

A low-cost, in-store dryer for small-scale farmers

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We developed a low-cost in-store dryer, called SRR-1, at UAF to meet the needs of small-scale farmers in Vietnam. They require a dryer with adequate capacity, high-quality dried grain, and reasonable investment and drying cost.

The design of the SRR-1 dryer is based on the principle of low-temperature in-store drying. The dryer consists of three components: a two-stage axial fan, an electric heater, and a bamboo mat drying bin (see figure).

The drying bin consists of two concentric bamboo mat cylinders, 0.4 and 1.5 m in diameter and 1.1 m high. The bin can contain 1 t of rough rice.

A 0.5-hp electric motor drives the fan. Two 350-mm-diameter rotors are mounted on both ends of the motor shaft inside a steel casing. (Plastic rotors are locally made and readily available in the market.) The fan is positioned on top of the inner bamboo mat cylinder; it can deliver $0.3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 400 Pa static pressure. The heater is a 1000-W resistor from an electric stove; it is mounted beneath the lower rotor. Supplemental heat from the resistor is sometimes used at night or during times of continuous rain.

During the day and the first two nights, the fan is turned on to aerate the rice. Supplementary heat is provided on the third night. In succeeding nights, the blower is turned off because the grain moisture content is low enough for temporary storage.

At an initial moisture content of 26-28% (wet basis), drying time is 80-85 h batch⁻¹, for which total power consumption is 80

Schematic of SRR-1 dryer.

kWh batch⁻¹. The dryer does not require much, and its manufacturing cost is less than US\$100. (SRR stands for “very cheap dryer” in Vietnamese). The aired grain quality from SRR is outstanding. Moisture gradients are less than 1%, and head rice recovery is increased by at least 2% when compared with sun drying—and the weather risk is eliminated. After drying, the

rice is stored in the drying bin and the fan is moved to the next bin.

Drying costs at UAF were \$5 batch⁻¹, including dryer depreciation. The dryer is designed for farm-level use, mainly for drying and storing rough rice for household consumption. More than 200 units were sold within 1 yr of introduction in Vietnam. Many farmers in southern Vietnam are enthusiastically accepting the SRR-1 dryer. ■